

A REFERENCE SPEECH RECOGNITION ALGORITHM FOR
BENCHMARKING AND SPEECH DATA BASE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

A complete connected word reference algorithm has been developed at NBS. It provides score statistics and confusibility measures as well as word decisions on the speech data base on which it is run. The basic algorithm is like the Bridle, Brown, and Chamberlain [1] algorithm with Euclidean distances on mel scale cepstral coefficients. There are options as to the particular spectral features, the type of spectral comparison measures and the training scheme. Score statistics are collected and a measure of confusibility is computed for each word in the vocabulary. The algorithm has been tested on the Texas Instruments Isolated Word Data Base [2]. The most confusable words in the data base are no and go. In addition the performance of the reference system has been compared with several generic types of recognizers.

Introduction

A problem with evaluating speech recognizers is that each of the recognizers has been developed to use in a certain environment, that is, background noise condition and communication channel. For this reason no one speech data base will be sufficient to show the best performance of several recognizers. The problem is how to fairly test speech recognizers on data for which they were designed and generalize the results to some meaningful figure of merit for each of the recognizers. Unfortunately there is no easy way to quantitatively measure the relative recognition difficulty of speech data bases which differ in vocabulary and environment.

One way to characterize the relative recognition difficulty of speech data bases is to use a reference speech recognition algorithm. Of course this measure of difficulty is valid only for the technology used in the reference algorithm. This type of algorithm must be in the public domain and provide score statistics and

confusibility measures as well as the usual word decisions. This approach was first suggested by R. K. Moore [3]. A preliminary isolated word algorithm for this purpose has been published by G. F. Chollet and C. Gagnoulet [4]. This algorithm was incomplete in that it did not incorporate programs for training or for collecting and plotting score statistics. It did include a confusibility measure.

Another use of the algorithm is as a benchmark against which other speech recognition systems are measured. Thus, on an arbitrary speech data base, a relative measure of performance can be made. While we have not made extensive studies, some comparison data is presented on the relative performance of generic types of speech recognizers to the reference algorithm.

A complete connected word reference algorithm has been developed at NBS. It is a speaker dependent one-pass dynamic time-warping algorithm like the one developed by Bridle, Brown and Chamberlain [1]. Several spectral analysis techniques are available within the algorithm (FFT, Band Energy and Mel Scale Cepstral Coefficients). Euclidean distance measures are used with optional "dead zones" to mimic simple human perceptual models. An averaged template training scheme is used with thresholds for the closeness of fit required for a merging. Normally this closeness of fit threshold is set so that words with optional release of the final plosive are clustered into two templates. In the recognition phase a graphics display (written for a Sun Microsystems Workstation) shows the tree of possibilities being searched, and dynamically displays the pruning of the tree to one word string. Score statistics are collected for each word in the vocabulary. A preliminary study of confusibility measures showed that ratios of best correct score to best incorrect score on a per utterance basis were the most reliable measures of confusibility. The algorithm is written in the "C" computer language for Unix operating systems and is available for distribution to interested parties.

Data Base Analysis

The algorithm was used to analyze the TI Isolated Word Data Base [2]. We report in detail the results of analyzing one speaker with initials HNJ. Since this is not a connected word data base, some of the difficulties of scoring connected word recognition are avoided. The particular spectral analysis technique is 6 mel scale cepstral coefficients with 20 msec Hamming windowed data. Figure 2 shows the score distribution of best correct score and best incorrect score for the templates yes and no.

Figure 2. Histogram of Word Scores

The word "yes" is not very similar acoustically to any other word in the data base, so the distribution could be two well separated Gaussians. However "no" is acoustically similar to "go" so that the distributions "no" longer appear well separated and the second best scores are very spread out. A measure of the overlap of these distributions, as suggested by Chollet and Gagnoulet [4] is not a very good indicator of confusibility. A better measure is the ratio of the best correct score to the best incorrect score on a per utterance basis. This is because the distance scores are not independent when there is considerable acoustic similarity. An anomalous word, that is one which is unusually spoken or poorly articulated, will have a high distance score to the correct template and the distance to nearest other word will also be high. In this case there is no danger of confusion if the ratio of these distances exceeds unity by a comfortable margin. A histogram of the ratios of distances is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Histogram of Ratios of Scores

The distribution is still not Gaussian, but shows the population in danger of confusion. Since utterances which have distances between same word and another word which differ by 20 % are seldom confused in practice, we define the number of probably confusable utterances to be those with ratios less than 1.2. A confusibility measure is obtained by converting this number to a percentage of probably confusable utterances. Figure 4 shows a comparison of this confusibility measure with the Chollet-Gagnoulet measure and the actual confusions. Our confusion measure predicts the confusions more accurately on this data set.

WORD	CHOLLET-GAGNOULET COMPLEXITY MEASURE	PERCENT PROBABLY CONFUSABLE WORDS	PERCENT ACTUAL CONFUSIONS
NO	2.17	18.75	0
GO	1.31	6.25	6.25
3	1.48	6.25	0
STOP	1.28	0	0
START	0.84	0	0
HELP	1.07	0	0
4	1.28	12.5	0
0	1.24	0	0
1	1.20	0	0
RUBOUT	1.05	0	0
REPEAT	1.04	0	0

Figure 4. Confusibility Measures

Testing Spectral Analysis Techniques

Since the reference algorithm offers three types of spectral analysis, different analysis techniques can be easily compared. Figure 5 shows a comparison of a 32 point FFT (5 msec window) and mel scale cepstral coefficients (6 and 12 coefficients with a 20 msec window). The mel scale cepstral coefficients are much better than the 32 FFT coefficients. Clearly the algorithm using 6 mel scale cepstral coefficients is superior to using 12 on this particular speaker for the TI vocabulary. Further studies of band energy based recognition with 20 msec analysis windows are planned.

FFT	MELCP 6	MELCP 12
89.5 %	99.7 %	98.2 %

Figure 5. Recognition Results

We are also studying perceptually motivated spectral comparison measures in our laboratory. Thus far attempts to model the amplitude discrimination of the human auditory system with dead zones in the comparison measures have failed to produce improved recognition. This is similar to the results of Blomberg et al who used perceptually scaled amplitude and masking in a recognition experiment [10].

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